

Kurtiella (Bivalvia, Montacutidae) in West Africa

Kurtiella (Bivalvia, Montacutidae) en África occidental

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ABSTRACT

West African representatives of the genus *Kurtiella* Gofas & Salas, 2008 are studied based on material collected mostly by dredging off Senegal and Angola. Four sympatric species are recognized, one of which is morphologically similar to the European type species of the genus, *K. bidentata*, and possibly conspecific. Previous records of *K. bidentata* from West Africa are shown to be based on other species, and three species are described as new. Two of the species described are among the smallest known bivalves, adult shells hardly exceeding one mm in length.

RESUMEN

Se estudian representantes del género *Kurtiella* Gofas y Salas, 2008 en África occidental, a partir de material recogido en su mayoría por dragado frente a Senegal y Angola. Se reconocen cuatro especies simpátricas, una de las cuales es morfológicamente muy similar a la especie tipo del género, *K. bidentata*, de Europa, y posiblemente coespecífica. Se muestra que citas anteriores de *K. bidentata* en África occidental corresponden a otras especies, y tres especies se describen como nuevas. Dos de las especies descritas como nuevas están entre los bivalvos más diminutos que se conocen, superando apenas un milímetro de longitud en la concha adulta.

INTRODUCTION

Small montacutids with a deep notch in the hinge plate and with two short but very distinct laterals on the right valve only, were distinguished by GOFAS & SALAS (2008) as a new genus, *Kurtiella*, and the name has since become widely used (e.g. COAN & VALENTICH-SCOTT, 2012; HUBER, 2015). The type species of the genus, *Kurtiella bidentata* (Montagu, 1803) is widespread, and quite common in European seas (OCKELMANN & MUUS, 1978; Ó FOIGHIL, MCGRATH, CONNEELY, KEEGAN & COSTELLO, 1984).

Representatives of the genus in West Africa are hardly known and it is not even clear if *K. bidentata*, like many other European bivalves, occurs also on the African coast south of Morocco. Reports in West Africa (LAMY, 1923; NICKLES, 1950; 1952; 1955) are scarce, and may as well apply to similar, but distinct species. Some material was available in the malacology collections in Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris (hereafter MNHN), nevertheless its study was postponed by GOFAS & SALAS (2008) and is here undertaken.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material examined herein was collected by the first author in the 1980s in Angola, by Igor Marche-Marchad in the 1950s in Senegal, and by the Danish "Atlantide" expedition along the West African coast in 1945-1946. The detail of specimens and localities is given with each species. Comparative material of *K. bidentata* and other European species is detailed in GOFAS & SALAS (2008). All specimens examined are deposited in Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, with the exception of those collected by "Atlantide" expedition which belong to Zoological Museum, University of Copenhagen.

The shells were cleaned and prepared for illustrations by soaking for ca. 15 minutes in a 10% solution of sodium-lauryl-sulphate (a pH-neuter detergent), then rinsed in tap water and laid over a surface of wet tissue and gently cleaned with a very fine paintbrush, under the stereomicroscope. Most specimens are far too fragile to undergo ultrasonic cleaning. Light photographs were taken using a Nikon DXM camera connected to a computer. Specimens examined

under SEM were placed on double sided adhesive copper tape, and metalized with gold prior to examination under the SEM. After imaging, specimens were unglued under a drop of water. Despite these precautions some specimens were fissured and one of them broke in two pieces from the tension of the adhesive. SEM micrographs were taken using a JEOL JSM-840 scanning electron microscope equipped with a digital camera.

Specimens were measured under a Leica MZ12 stereomicroscope, using a reticule built into a 10x eyepiece at standard magnifications of x10 (for shells) and x100 (for prodissoconchs). The accuracy of the reticule in the selected magnification was first checked with a stage micrometre scale representing 10 mm graduated every 0.1 mm.

Abbreviations used

h/l: height (dorso-ventral)/length (antero-posterior)
w/l: width/length
spm.: specimen (live taken)
sta.: sampling station
v.: valve

SYSTEMATIC PART

Kurtiella cf. bidentata (Montagu 1803) (Figs. 1, 2)

Mya bidentata Montagu 1803

Mysella bidentata (Montagu 1803): Ockelmann & Muus, 1978 (biology and behaviour)

Kurtiella bidentata (Montagu, 1803): Gofas & Salas, 2008

Material examined: France, Brittany — 315 spm (0.96x0.76 to 3.64x2.46 mm). Spain and Morocco — 98 spm. (0.96x0.74 to 3.00x2.16 mm), 20 sh. and 987 v. (0.92x0.72 to 3.50x2.42 mm; prodissoconch 0.40 to 0.48 mm), see Gofas & Salas, 2008 supplementary material for details. Sénégal — Baie de Gorée, 80-250 m, leg. Marche-Marchad, 1 v. (2.66 x 1.92 mm). Angola — Off Cabo Ledo, (approx. 09°36'S, 13°06'E, 40 m), 17 spm. (1.22 x 0.86 to 2.14 x 1.52 mm; prodissoconchs 0.32 to 0.40 mm) and 2 v. (1.22 x 0.90 mm); Off Mussulo (08°50'S, 13°05'E, 90 m), 10 v. (1.40 x 1.20 to 2.67 x 2.05 mm); Barra do Dande (08°28.1'S, 13°21.6'E, low tide level), 4 spm. (1.32 x 0.98 to 1.40 x 1.04 mm, prodissoconchs 0.36 to 0.40 mm) and 5 v. (1.04 x 0.78 to 1.50 x 1.10 mm)

Description (based on Angolan specimens): Shell just over 2.1 mm in length (h/l ratio 0.74), compressed (w/l ratio 0.4), equivalve, inequilateral, moderately robust. Outline nearly oval. Ante-

rior part of dorsal margin at first nearly straight, then gradually merging into the evenly rounded anterior margin. Ventral margin slightly convex. Postero-dorsal margin at first forming a small

Figure 1. *Kurtiella* cf. *bidentata* (Montagu, 1803), off Cabo Ledo, Angola. A: inner view of left valve; B: inner view of right valve; C: outer view of right valve, length 2.1 mm.

Figura 1. *Kurtiella* cf. *bidentata* (Montagu, 1803), frente a Cabo Ledo, Angola. A: vista interna de la valva izquierda; B: vista interna de la valva derecha; C: vista externa de la valva derecha, longitud 2,1 mm.

embayment just behind the umbo, then convex. Posterior margin convex, with the maximum convexity at the transitions to postero-dorsal and ventral margins. Inner edges of valves smooth and tightly appressed ventrally.

Beaks situated towards the posterior 1/3rd, slightly opisthogyrate. Prodissoconch 320-400 μ m in diameter, with distinct prodissoconchs 1 and 2. Dissoconch with weak sculpture of fine comarginal lines only.

Hinge plate moderately thick, extending dorsally on either side of the beaks, over approximately half of the shell length, interrupted beneath the beaks by a notch in which a large internal ligament is lodged. Lateral teeth well marked and diverging ca. 100° on right valve, hardly more than a swelling of hinge plate and diverging ca. 120° on left valve. Lunule and escutcheon indistinct.

Adductor scars subequal, dorsoventrally elongate; pallial line thick, continuous, parallel to the ventral margin.

Shell colour white on dissoconch and prodissoconch, with yellowish periostracum.

Remarks: A notable variation in the outline, which may be more or less elongate, more or less evenly rounded on the posterior end appears among the specimens identified as *K. bidentata* everywhere. OCKELMANN & MUUS (1978) found two morphologically distinct forms living in close localities in northern Øresund, Denmark. On these grounds, the Senegalese and Angolan specimens studied here would have been identified unambiguously as *K. bidentata*, had they been collected within the known range of the species. The apparently large gap in its distribution may be an artefact due to the rarity of the species, or alternately some isolated populations may occur. Whether *Kurtiella bidentata* represents a single species, as represented in the literature, or multiple cryptic species with narrower distributions is an issue that

Figure 2. *Kurtiella* cf. *bidentata* (Montagu, 1803), off Cabo Ledo, Angola, SEM micrographs. A-D: same specimen as Figure 1, length 2.1 mm. A: inner view of the left valve; B: inner view of the right valve; C: detail of the hinge of the left valve; D: detail of the hinge of the right valve; the space between teeth is occupied by remnants of the ligament. E: right valve from the same locality, outer view, length 1.52 mm. F: prodissoconch of the left valve of another shell. G: detail of prodissoconch 1, same valve as F.

Figura 2. Kurtiella cf. *bidentata* (Montagu, 1803), frente a Cabo Ledo, Angola, micrografías al MEB. A-D: mismo ejemplar que en la Figura 1, longitud 2,1 mm. A: vista interna de la valva izquierda; B: vista interna de la valva derecha; C: detalle de la charnela de la valva izquierda; D: detalle de la charnela de la valva derecha; el espacio entre los dientes está ocupada por restos de ligamento. E: valva derecha de la misma localidad, vista externa, longitud 1,52 mm. F: prodissoconcha de la valva izquierda de otra concha. G: detalle de la prodissoconcha 1, misma valva que F.

Figure 3. *Kurtiella* sp. (undescribed), one of the shells identified as *Montacuta bidentata* by Nicklès (1955). Locality: “Atlantide” sta. 136, off Luanda (Angola). Size 6.8 mm.

Figura 3. *Kurtiella* sp. (no descrita), una de las conchas identificadas como *Montacuta bidentata* by Nicklès (1955). Localidad: “Atlantide” sta. 136, off Luanda (Angola). Tamaño 6,8 mm.

should probably be clarified with genetic studies.

Conversely, none of the specimens collected by the “Atlantide” expedition and cited by NICKLÈS (1955) as *Montacuta bidentata* are this species. Some of them (see below) could be large valves of *Kurtiella africana* spec. nov. whereas

others from “Atlantide” sta. 57, 64, 66 and 136 represent a further undescribed species (Figure 3) currently under study by Rudo von Cosel (pers. comm.) and also figured in HUBER (2015: 156) as *Kurtiella* sp. 3. The valve cited by LAMY (1923) from Guinea-Bissau could not be traced in MNHN.

Kurtiella africana spec. nov. (Figs. 4-7)

Type material: Holotype (MNHN-IM 2000-31629): complete shell, 2.7 mm, coated for SEM. Paratypes (MNHN-IM 2000-31629): 4 sh. and 10 valves from the type locality, all leg. Gofas, 1981-1985, in Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle, Paris.

Material examined: Senegal — SW of Madeleines (45-46 m), 1 sh. (2.68 x 1.72 mm) and 1 v. (3.54 x 2.16 mm, prodissoconch 0.48 mm), leg. Marche-Marchad 9.i.1954; Off Gorée (50 m), 1 v. (4.47 x 2.74 mm), leg. Marche-Marchad 5.vii.1955; SW of Gorée (14°41’N, 17°23.2’W, 17 m), 2 v. (3.24 x 2.06 to 3.46 x 2.18 mm), leg. R. von Cosel 24.iii.1988. Liberia — “Atlantide” sta. 56 (06°01’N, 10°26’W, 50-55 m), 2 v. (5.3 x 3.3 mm, 6.5 x 4.1 mm). Angola — “Atlantide” sta. 129 (06°15’S, 12°20’E, 12 m), 2 valves (broken). Corimba (08°51.0’S, 13°10.5’E, 10-20 m on sand bar), 5 sh. (1.56 x 1.08 to 2.64 x 1.64 mm) and 44 v. (2.48 x 1.52 to 3.22 x 2.10 mm; prodissoconchs 0.58 to 0.62 mm), includes the type material. Off Mussulo (08°50’S, 13°05’E, 90 m), 60 v. (1.26 x 0.94 to 3.68 x 2.30 mm; prodissoconchs 0.52 to 0.70 mm); Off Ilha de Luanda (08°44’S, 13°12’E, 40-60 m), 8 sh. (0.82 x 0.64 to 1.68 x 1.14 mm) and 16 v. (1.40 x 1.00 to 3.56 x 2.20 mm; prodissoconchs 0.52 to 0.68 mm)

Type locality: Corimba (08°51.0’S, 13°10.5’E, 10-20 m on sand bar), Angola.

Etymology: named after Africa, as being the least rare species of *Kurtiella* found in West Africa.

Figure 4. *Kurtiella africana* spec. nov., Corimba (20 m), Angola. A: inner view of a left valve (paratype), length 2.85 mm. B: inner view of a right valve (paratype), length 2.50 mm; C: outer view of the same valve.

Figura 4. *Kurtiella africana* spec. nov., Corimba (20 m), Angola. A: vista interna de una valva izquierda (paratipo), longitud 2,85 mm. B: vista interna de una valva derecha (paratipo), longitud 2,50 mm; C: vista externa de la misma valva.

Description: Shell up to 3.5 mm (exceptionally over 4 mm) in length (mean h/l ratio 0.64), compressed (w/l ratio 0.37), equivalve, inequilateral, thin and fragile. Outline nearly oval. Anterior part of dorsal margin at first gently curved, then gradually merging into the evenly rounded anterior margin. Ventral margin slightly convex. Postero-dorsal margin at first forming a distinct embayment just behind the umbo, then becoming evenly convex. Posterior margin slightly convex, less so than the transitions to postero-dorsal and to ventral margins, so as to make it appear indistinctly truncated. Inner edges of valves smooth, tightly appressed ventrally.

Beaks situated towards the posterior 1/3rd, slightly opisthogyrate. Prodissoconch 520-580 μ m in maximum diameter, with distinct prodissoconchs 1 and 2. Prodissoconch 1 smooth, elongate, about 100 μ m in its maximum diameter, distinctly bulging over the surface of prodissoconch 2, which is subcircular, convex, ornamented with faint growth lines. Dis-

soconch with very fine growth lines and with a microsculpture of antimarginal threads, grossly parallel but occasionally converging or diverging, the spacing being maintained by insertion or suppression of additional threads (Fig. 5H).

Hinge plate narrow, extending dorsally on either sides of the beaks, over approximately half of the shell length, interrupted beneath the beaks by a notch in which a large internal ligament is lodged. Lateral teeth narrow and thin but well-marked on the right valve, diverging ca. 130° and slightly bent so as to be even more divergent in their distal part; hardly more than a swelling of hinge plate on the left valve. Lunule and escutcheon indistinct. Adductor scars subequal, irregularly shaped, dorsoventrally elongate; pallial line moderately thick, continuous.

Shell colour generally white on dissoconch; on fresh shells the prodissoconch has a yellowish hue.

Remarks: Compared to *Kurtiella bidentata*, *K. africana* is about the same size but

Figure 5. *Kurtiella africana* spec. nov., Corimba (20 m), Angola, SEM micrographs. A-D: holotype, length 2.7 mm. A: inner view of the left valve; B: inner view of the right valve; C: detail of the hinge of the left valve; D: detail of the hinge of the right valve. E-H: Right valve from the type locality, length 3.05 mm. E: outer view; F: prodissoconch; G: detail of the prodissoconch-dissoconch transition; H: Detail of the microsculpture of the dissoconch near the ventral margin.

Figura 5. Kurtiella africana spec. nov., Corimba (20 m), Angola, micrografías al MEB. A-D: holotipo, longitud 2,7 mm. A: vista interna de la valva izquierda; B: vista interna de la valva derecha; C: detalle de la charnela de la valva izquierda; D: detalle de la charnela de la valva derecha. E-H: valva derecha de la localidad tipo, longitud 3,05 mm. E: vista externa; F: prodissoconcha; G: detalle de la transición prodissoconcha-dissoconcha; H: detalle de la microscultura de dissoconcha cerca del borde ventral.

Figure 6. *Kurtiella africana* spec. nov., off Ilha de Luanda (40-60 m), Angola, SEM micrographs. A: inner view of a left valve, actual length 2.90 mm; B: Inner view of a right valve, length 3.20 mm; C: detail of the hinge of the left valve; D: detail of the hinge of the right valve. E: Prodissoconch 1, same valve as B; F: Prodissoconch of a right valve; G: detail of the prodissoconch 1, same valve as F. *Figura 6. Kurtiella africana spec. nov., frente a Ilha de Luanda (40-60 m), Angola, micrografías al MEB. A: Vista interna de una valva izquierda, longitud 2,90 mm; B: Vista interna de una valva derecha, longitud 3,20 mm; C: detalle de la charnela de la valva izquierda; D: detalle de la charnela de la valva derecha. E: Prodissoconcha 1, misma valva que B; F: Prodissoconcha de una valva derecha; G: detalle de la prodissoconcha 1, misma valva que F.*

proportionally more elongate (h/l 0.64 instead of 0.74 or more), has a thinner shell and almost always a distinct antimarginal microsculpture. Some specimens of *K.*

bidentata may have indeed an antimarginal sculpture (see GOFAS & SALAS, 2008: fig. 8I) but this sculpture is blurry, indistinct. The teeth of the right valve are more

Figure 7. *Kurtiella africana* spec. nov., “Atlantide” sta. 56 (50-55 m), Liberia. A: outer view of a right valve, length 5.3 mm. B: inner view of the same valve. C: detail of microsculpture. D: prodisoconch.

Figura 7. *Kurtiella africana* spec. nov., “Atlantide” sta. 56 (50-55 m), Liberia. A: vista externa de una valva derecha, length 5.3 mm. B: vista interna de la misma valva. C: detalle de la microescultura; D: prodisoconcha.

bulging, definitely thicker distally in *K. bidentata*, and are not bent as in *K. africana* spec. nov. Another conspicuous difference is seen in the prodisoconch, which is larger than that of *K. bidentata* and has yellowish hue in the fresh shells, whereas in *K. bidentata* it is invariably white.

The undescribed species illustrated on Figure 3 resembles *K. africana* spec. nov. in the outline of early growth stages. However it differs in being much more elongate, with the umbo situated more posteriorly, in having an unobvious microsculpture, in the teeth of the left valve developed as conspicuously raised blades instead of being mere swellings of the hinge plate, and in the insertion of the pallial line, which departs from the posterior adductor scar in a nearly horizontal course instead of downwards like in

most species including *K. africana* spec. nov. (compare Fig. 3A with Fig. 4A and 7B).

Some specimens of *K. africana* spec. nov., particularly those collected in deeper waters (90 -100 m) have a less conspicuous microsculpture, but still they have a hint of microstriae; and the size of the prodisoconch in those specimens coincides with the measurements from shallower samples.

This species could grow larger than the size range represented in our Angolan material. The valves illustrated by HUBER (2015: 156) as *Kurtiella* sp. 2 could be this species although their prodisoconch is not obviously coloured, and are twice as large. The valves from Liberia collected at “Atlantide” sta. 56 are most likely conspecific and the largest one is 6.3 mm long.

Figure 8. *Kurtiella piscatorum* spec. nov., off Mussulo (90 m), Angola. A: inner view of a left valve (paratype), length 1.40 mm. B: inner view of a right valve (paratype), length 1.42 mm; C: outer view of the same valve.

Figura 8. *Kurtiella piscatorum* spec. nov., frente a Mussulo (90 m), Angola. A: vista interna de una valva izquierda (paratipo), longitud 1,40 mm. B: vista interna de una valva derecha (paratipo), longitud 1,42 mm; C: vista exterior de la misma valva.

Kurtiella piscatorum spec. nov. (Figs. 8, 9)

Type material: Holotype (MNHN-IM 2000-31631): complete shell, 1.30 mm, coated for SEM. Paratypes (MNHN-IM 2000-31632): 2 sh. and 10 valves from the type locality, all leg. Gofas, 1981-1985, in Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris.

Material examined: Angola — Off Mussulo (08°50'S, 13°05'E, 90 m), 3 sh. (1.26 x 0.96 to 1.46 x 1.04) and 14 v. (1.08 x 0.88 to 1.42 x 1.04 mm; prodissoconchs 0.42 to 0.50 mm), includes the type material; Off Ilha de Luanda (08°44'S, 13°12'E, 40-60 m), 5 v. (1.22 x 0.88 to 1.60 x 1.20 mm, prodissoconch 0.48 mm).

Type locality: Off Mussulo (08°50'S, 13°05'E, 90 m), Angola.

Etymology: From the Latin, *piscator*. *-is* (genitive plural *-orum*), named to honour the local fishermen who guided the first author to productive localities off the coast of Luanda.

Description: Shell up to 1.6 mm in length (mean h/l ratio 0.73), somewhat inflated (w/l ratio 0.46), equivalve, inequilateral, fragile. Outline nearly oval. Anterior part of dorsal margin gently sloping, then gradually merging into the evenly rounded anterior margin. Ventral margin moderately convex. Postero-dorsal margin some-

what concave just behind the umbo, then convex. Posterior margin slightly convex, less so than the transitions to postero-dorsal and to ventral margins, so as to make it appear definitely truncated. Inner edges of valves smooth and tightly appressed ventrally.

Beaks situated towards the posterior 1/3rd, slightly opisthogyrate. Prodisso-

Figure 9. *Kurtiella piscatorum* spec. nov. from Angola, SEM micrographs. A-D: holotype, off Mussulo (90 m), length 1.30 mm. A: inner view of the left valve; B: inner view of the right valve; C: detail of the hinge of the left valve; D: detail of the hinge of the right valve. E: outer view of a left valve from the type locality, length 1.42 mm; F: prodissoconch of another shell from the type locality, viewed from the right valve; G: detail of the prodissoconch 1 of the same shell; H: prodissoconch 1 of a valve from off Ilha de Luanda (40-60 m).

Figura 9. Kurtiella piscatorum spec. nov. de Angola, micrografías al MEB. A-D: holotipo, frente a Mussulo (90 m), longitud 1,30 mm. A: vista interna de la valva izquierda; B: vista interna de la valva derecha; C: detalle de la charnela de la valva izquierda; D: detalle de la charnela de la valva derecha. E: vista externa de una valva izquierda de la localidad tipo, longitud 1,42 mm; F: prodissoconcha de otra concha de la localidad tipo, vista desde la valva derecha; G: detalle de la prodissoconcha 1 del mismo ejemplar; H: prodissoconcha 1 de una valva de frente a Ilha de Luanda (40-60 m).

conch 420-500 μm in maximum diameter, with distinct prodissoconchs 1 and 2. Prodissoconch 1 with pitted microsculpture on central part and smooth ventral edge, slightly more than 100 μm in its maximum diameter, distinctly bulging over the surface of prodissoconch 2, which is subcircular, convex, ornamented with inconspicuous growth lines. Dissoconch with very fine, dense, incised commarginal lines only.

Hinge plate moderately thick in proportion to the shell, extending dorsally on either side of the beaks, over approximately half of the shell length, interrupted beneath the beaks by a notch in which a large internal ligament is lodged. Lateral teeth on the right valve narrow but strong and elevated, parallel-sided, diverging ca. 100°; hardly more than a swelling of hinge plate on the left valve. Lunule indistinct, but posterior escutcheon quite distinct on the

left valve. Adductor scars and pallial line indistinct; scars subequal, dorsoventrally elongate; pallial line moderately thick, continuous, parallel to the ventral margin. Shell colour uniformly white.

Remarks: The most striking character of this species is the shape of the teeth in the right valve, which are prominent, parallel sided, and clearly less divergent than in the other three species discussed here. The outline is more convex ventrally and more definitely truncated posteriorly than in *K. bidentata*, and thereby recalls that of some minute protobranchs of the genus *Microgloma*. The prodissoconch 1 is somewhat pitted, a character state shared with the European deep-water species *Kurtiella ovata* (Jeffreys, 1881), which is otherwise very different in having a brownish prodissoconch, and a larger and more compressed shell with clearly opisthogyrate umbos.

Kurtiella tertia spec. nov. (Figs. 10-11)

Type material: Holotype (MNHN-IM 2000-31633): complete shell, 1.27 mm, coated for SEM. Paratypes (MNHN-IM 2000-31634): 2 spm. and 10 sh. from the type locality, all leg. Gofas, 1981-1985, in Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris.

Material examined: Angola — Off Mussulo (08°50'S, 13°05'E, 90 m), 2 spm. (1.08 x 0.80 to 1.18 x 0.90), 59 sh. (0.68 x 0.46 to 1.27 x 0.95 mm, prodissoconchs 0.32 to 0.38 mm) and 34 v.; includes the type material; Off Ilha de Luanda (08°44'S, 13°12'E, 40-60 m), 8 sh. (0.78 x 0.58 to 1.04 x 0.81 mm) and 16 v.

Type locality: Off Mussulo (08°50'S, 13°05'E, 90 m), Angola.

Etymology: From the Latin adjective *tertius*, *-a*, *-um*, so named as being the third sympatric species of *Kurtiella* in the type locality.

Description: Shell up to 1.2 mm in length with mean l/h ratio of 1.3 in adults, somewhat compressed (w/l ratio 0.39), equivalve, inequilateral, fragile. Outline oval tending to subquadrangular. Anterior part of dorsal margin at first very gently sloping, then quite abruptly merging into the evenly rounded anterior margin. Ventral margin moderately convex. Postero-dorsal margin slightly concave over some distance behind the umbo, then convex. Posterior margin slightly convex, less so than the transitions to postero-dorsal and to ventral margins, so as to make it appear somewhat truncated. Inner edges of valves smooth and tightly appressed ventrally.

Beaks situated towards the posterior 1/3rd, very slightly opisthogyrate. Prodissoconch 320-380 μm in maximum diameter, with distinct prodissoconchs 1 and 2. Prodissoconch 1 rather smooth, about 90 μm in its maximum diameter, nearly flush with the surface of prodissoconch 2, which is subcircular, convex, ornamented with faint growth lines. Dissoconch with very fine commarginal lines only.

Hinge plate rather narrow, extending dorsally on either sides of the beaks, over approximately half of the shell length, interrupted beneath the beaks by a notch in which a large internal ligament is lodged. Lateral teeth on the

Figure 10. *Kurtiella tertia* spec. nov. from off Mussulo (90 m), Angola. A-C: complete shell (paratype) from the type locality, length 1.00 mm. A: inner view of the left valve; B: inner view of the right valve; C: outer view of the right valve. D: another complete shell (paratype) viewed from the right valve, size 1.00 mm.

Figura 10. *Kurtiella tertia* spec. nov., frente a Mussulo (90 m), Angola. A-C: concha completa (paratipo) de la localidad tipo, longitud 1,00 mm.: A: Vista interna de la valva izquierda; B: vista interna de la valva derecha; C: vista externa de la valva derecha. D: otra concha completa (paratipo) vista desde la valva derecha, tamaño 1,00 mm.

right valve narrow and slender, diverging ca. 110° , almost parallel to the dorsal margin; hardly more than a swelling of hinge plate on the left valve. Lunule and escutcheon indistinct. Adductor scars and pallial line indistinct. Shell colour uniformly white.

Remarks: This tiny species is represented in our material by the largest number of complete shells and is the only one of the new species collected alive. Compared to specimens of *K. pis-*

catorum spec. nov. of similar size occurring in the same sample, it is readily distinguished by its outline which is higher in proportion to the length and has the concave stretch of postero-dorsal margin extending over about one-third of the shell, whereas it is very short on most species. The configuration of the teeth, nearly parallel to the dorsal margin, is clearly different from that of *K. piscatorum* which are much more prominent and pointing downwards.

Figure 11. *Kurtiella tertia* spec. nov. from Angola, SEM micrographs. A-D: holotype from off Mussulo (90 m), length 1.27 mm. A: inner view of the left valve; B: Inner view of the right valve; C: detail of the hinge of the left valve; D: detail of the hinge of the right valve. E: prodissoconch of another shell (paratype) from the type locality, viewed from the right valve. F: detail of the prodissoconch 1 of the same shell.

Figura 11. Kurtiella tertia spec. nov. de Angola, micrografías al MEB. A-D: Concha (paratipo), frente a Mussulo (90 m), longitud 1,27 mm. A: vista interna de la valva izquierda; B: vista interna de la valva derecha; C: detalle de la charnela de la valva izquierda; D: detalle de la charnela de la valva derecha. E: prodisoconcha de otra concha de la localidad tipo, vista desde la valva derecha. F: detalle de la prodisoconcha 1 del mismo ejemplar.

DISCUSSION

Compared to temperate European seas, the species richness is comparable (2 shallow-water and three deep-sea species in the European northeast Atlantic, four or five shallow water species in West Africa) but the latter are considerably more rare. Very few living specimens were obtained

from a continued sampling effort over five years, which has yielded hundreds of lots and thousands of specimens. There were no *Kurtiella* in the localities of Southern Angola, also thoroughly sampled (see. e.g. GOFAS, 1989 for localities examined). Conversely, in the European Atlantic, *Kurtiella*

bidentata is not only a common species, but stands among the species which are taken into account in ecological surveys as a quantitatively significant component of the benthos (e.g. Ó FOIGHIL *ET AL.*, 1984; O'CONNOR, MCGRATH & KEEGAN, 1987; KÜNITZER, 1989; PREVEDELLI, SIMONINI & ANSALONI, 2001).

The prodissoconch of most Eastern Atlantic species of *Kurtiella*, including the four species treated herein, comprises well differentiated prodissoconchs 1 and 2, indicative of a planktonic, planktotrophic development which should ensure long distance dispersal. The West African region nevertheless hosts three species which apparently are found neither in temperate Ibero-Moroccan waters, nor in temperate Southern Angola. A similar distribution was observed with small gastropods of the family Rissoidae, among which species pairs with planktotrophic development would occupy the West African and temperate European areas, respectively (GOFAS, 1999). The Mauri-

tanian upwelling would be a barrier for the dispersal of larvae of tropical West African species (LE LOEUFF & COSEL, 1998; LONGHURST, 1998: 173-174).

This paper is based on a material that was collected along a small portion of the West African coast and certainly does not complete the inventory of West African *Kurtiella*. At least one more species is here reported as undescribed and nothing is known about possible deep-water species. Nevertheless, even taking this into account, *Kurtiella* can be qualified as rare in West Africa.

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